

Photochemical transformations of chromones[†]

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The photochemical transformations occurring in the chromones through cycloadditions, oxidations and reorganizations have been reviewed.

Chromones¹ constitute one of the major class of compounds occurring in the plant kingdom. These compounds, together with a number of their synthetic analogues, are biologically active in a variety of ways : they (i) exhibit biocide activity, especially as fungicides and bactericides², (ii) can act as antioxidants, due to their capacity to chelate metal ions or scavenge free radicals³, (iii) demonstrate a broad spectrum of biological activity in mammalian cell systems, particularly by inhibiting the growth of carcinoma cells and proliferation of some tumours⁴. Flavoxate (Uri spas)², a flavone derivative, is a well-known antispasmodic agent. The chromones have also found applications in dyeing technology, for example, quercetine⁵ a pentahydroxy flavone, has been used as a yellow dye for hundreds of years.

The chromones as they are present in all parts of the plants get exposed to sunlight for long durations of time that makes chromones liable to undergo structural transformations. Photochemistry is concerned with the physical changes resulting from the absorption of UV-visible light (200–800 nm) leading to the electronically excited states that may then proceed to give photoproducts.

Flavone (2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran) is known to act as a photodynamic transferring agent and has been shown to bring about *cis-trans* isomerisation⁶ in stilbenes. A similar isomerisation, observed in β -D-glucosyl-*o*-hydroxy cinnamic acid⁷, present in leaves, has been rationalized on similar lines.

Chromones are known to undergo photocycloadditions, photooxygenations and photoisomerisations involving $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The pyrone moiety in these heterocycles is non-aromatic like γ -pyrones; thus the double bond and C=O group may participate either in isolation or in conjugation with each other in the photochemical reactions.

In photocycloadditions, chromones are known to pro-

vide products by [2+2] π additions. They also add to 1,3-dipoles giving [3+2] π cycloadducts. The [2+2] π photocycloaddition reactions of chromones with different alkenes and alkynes have been extensively studied by Hanifin and Cohen⁸. These addition reactions involve an electrophilic attack by C-3 of chromone through $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ excitation on the alkene producing 1,4-biradical that closes to cyclobutanes **1** and **2** or cyclobutenes depending upon whether alkene or alkyne has been used.

2-Cyanochromones when reacted with ethylenes produced both [2+2] π and [3+2] π cycloadducts⁹ (**3** and **4**).

These cycloadditions have been rationalized through the involvement of an iminyl biradical (**5**); carrying out the reaction in presence of oxygen has provided the proof for this biradical.

The cycloaddition reactions have been applied towards the synthesis of marine sesquiterpene filiformin and conge-

[†]Dedicated to my teacher Professor S. M. Mukherji.

ners¹⁰. A reaction between ethylene and 3-alkoxychromones has been used to obtain a tetracyclic intermediate (**6**) which then was converted by acid-catalyzed reaction to produce the terpenes. The photocycloaddition product is formed through a tandem cycloaddition and γ -hydrogen abstraction sequence.

Photooxidation¹¹ of chromones lead to a wide variety of products through reorganization and degradations. For example, photo-oxidation of 3-hydroxyflavone has been found to yield **8** through the intermediate formation of **7**.

3-Hydroxyflavones on exposure to light under anaerobic conditions, exhibit sufficient photolability in spite of H-bonding. A 3-hydroxyflavone¹² on irradiation, photoisomerised to benzofuranone (**9**) in high yields. Such rearrangements are similar to those exhibited by 2,6-dimethyl- γ -pyrone¹³.

When an alkoxy group, instead of hydroxy group is present at position 3 of the chromone¹⁴, the reaction occurs through different route to give tetracyclic photoproducts (**10** and **11**) along with some other minor products.

Such photocyclisations have also been studied on Karanjin¹⁵ (**12**).

Addition reactions of benzophenone or other ketones failed on the double bond of furyl moiety in Karanjin although such additions of carbonyls have successfully been carried out in furanocoumarins¹⁶.

In a study on several 3-benzyloxy-2-phenyl derivatives of chromone¹⁷ (**13**), it was found that the rates of photocyclisations were much faster than that of 3-methoxychromones.

In the above photocyclisations it has been found that products **14** and **15** are formed independently from **13**; **15**, on photoirradiation with exclusion of oxidants (I_2/O_2), gave only polymeric products instead of being converted into **14**. These photocyclisations have been rationalized through the initial abstraction of hydrogen from 3-alkoxy group by the excited carbonyl of the pyrone moiety giving rise to **16** which then can either photo-dehydrogenate to produce **14** or may rearrange to **15** through 1,7-hydrogen migration.

The photochemistry of five-membered heterocyclic ring¹⁸ compounds in the past has attracted a lot of attention due to their high electron density – five atoms and six electrons and inherent aromatic character. The emphasis has been to compare their photochemical properties with those of six-membered rings having the same number of electrons. The five-membered heterocyclic rings have different stabilization energies : furan ~16 kcal, pyrrole ~21 kcal and thiophene ~32 kcal/mol. We have investigated the photochemistry of chromones carrying thiophenes and furans.

The photoreorganisation of 3-alkoxy-2-thienylchromones¹⁹ (17) have been found to undergo photocyclisations to give 18 and 19 in a manner similar to that as described above.

It is important to mention here that in alkyl/aryl thiophenes²⁰, phototranspositions through ring opening and isomerisation occur frequently but in the present study all our attempts to observe such a mode of reaction proved unsuccessful. Even in the photolysis of 2-(2'-thienyl)chromone no such phototranspositions could be observed.

In the phototransformation of 3-alkoxy-2-(2'-furyl)chromones²¹ no dehydrogenated product like 19 could be isolated. The primary product formed was a dihydrofuryl derivative 21 that underwent further photoreorganisation to a cyclopropylcarbonyl derivative 22 through a ring expansion and ring contraction mechanism when the reaction was carried in an aprotic solvent like benzene. The photoirradiation of 3-benzyloxy derivative of 2-(2'-furyl)chromone 20 (R = H) in methanol solvent not only

produced the dihydro product and cyclopropylaldehyde derivative but also gave a tricyclic methyl ester (23). Such transformations have been rationalized as shown below.

It has been observed that the formation and distribution of the cyclized and dehydrogenated product like 14, 15, 18, 19 and 21 in the photoirradiation of 3-alkoxy-2-arylchromones depend upon the electron density in aryl ring at C-2 (Table 1).

Table 1

Compd.	A	B	Ratio of A : B
			1 : 0 ²¹
			1 : 0 ²¹
			1 : 0
			1 : 0.2
			1 : 4 ¹⁷

2,3-Diphenyl-7-methoxychromone (24) in methanol, on photoirradiation, isomerises to isocoumarin²² (25), which then, through 6 π -electrocyclization, provides 26. In the formation of 25, a cleavage of 3,4-bond and subsequent for-

mation of cyclobutene intermediate has been thought to be involved.

From our laboratory, a reaction on 2-methyl-3,5,7-trimethoxychromone²³ (27) has been reported where H-abstraction coupled with dimerisation has led to the formation of a dimeric oxetanol (28). Such reactions have also been observed with 2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone²⁴.

In a recent study on 2,7-dimethyl-3-methoxychromone, Mandal *et al.*²⁵ have observed the formation of a similar dimeric oxetanol (29). But they have also reported that chromones (30) bearing no substituent on the benzenoid moiety did not undergo dimeric oxetanol formation but instead lead to the formation of demethoxylated products (31).

The demethoxylations here have been suggested by the authors to occur through a conjugate addition of methanol on 2,3-double bond of chromone followed by γ -H abstraction and double methoxy elimination.

Rotenones (32), a naturally occurring insecticide is a modified flavonoid²⁶, which on photooxygenation has been reported to give rotenanones (33). This provides an example of a biogenetic type of synthesis. The lactonisation observed here has also been seen in the photolysis of chromones²⁷ (34) when oxygen was bubbled through the reaction mixture.

In an unsensitised photooxygenation reaction photochromic 3-benzoylchromones (35) photoenolises²⁸ to diene (36),

which on reaction with singlet O₂ provided 37 whose decomposition gave 2,3-dibenzoylchromone (38).

2-Benzylchromone²⁸ (35) can photoenolise to 36 and 36a that then can isomerise to lead to two linear photoproducts (39 and 40) under anaerobic conditions.

A conrotatory ring closure utilizing the triene system available in 2-styrylchromones (**41** and **43**) has found use in the synthesis of angular tetracyclic heterocyclic compounds²⁹ (**42** and **44**) respectively.

The photocyclisations have been employed towards the synthesis of linearly fused 2,3-pyranobenzopyrones. The photoirradiation of 3-benzyloxy-2-styrylchromones³⁰ has been found to yield a linearly fused tricyclic pyrane compound (**45**). The reaction occurs through an initial H-abstraction from 3-benzyloxy group by the excited C=O group.

Spiropyrans find extensive use in information and storage technology and the few methods³¹ developed earlier involve [4+2] π cycloadditions, reductive thermal cyclisations and enamine elimination etc. In our laboratory a general and photochemical approach towards the synthesis of complex spiropyrans³² (**46** and **47**) has been developed.

The routes available in the literature for the synthesis of

vinyl ethers³³ are quite involved; we recently have reported a one step photochemical isomerisation of allyl ethers (**48**) to vinyl ethers³⁴ (**49**).

It has been inferred in these experiments that the presence of an electron-captive group like $-\text{COOCH}_3$ is essential for such photoisomerisations, a fact corroborated by the observation that photolysis of simple allyl ethers³⁵ of these chromones (**50** and **51**) produced only photocyclised products (**52**, **53** and **54**).

Thiones³⁶ have similar chemical properties as the analogous ketones but their photochemical behaviour differ to quite an extent. This could be due to the different electronegativities of oxygen and sulphur. We studied the

photocyclisations of 3-alkoxythiochromones³⁷ (**55** and **56**) and have observed that only those thiochromones that carry benzyloxy group ($R = C_6H_5$) undergo reactions and, in contrast, 3-alkoxythiochromones ($R = H, CH_3$) failed to undergo any photoreactions.

Some photoisomerisations³⁸ of 3-aryl and 3'-(2-furyl)-2-(2-furyl)chromones (**57**) have been studied for generation of fluorophores. Various substituents in aryl and furyl groups have been introduced to study the efficacy of these fluorophores.

Intramolecular bichromophoric interactions³⁹ in

bisanthracenes, biscoumarins, bispyrones and bisalkoxybenzophenones have been the subject of interest both to spectroscopists as well as to chemists. The role of spacer in the product formation in the photolysis of bischromones built around alkyl chains⁴⁰ of varying lengths (**58** and **59**), and xyllyl moieties⁴¹ (**60** and **61**) has been examined in our laboratory.

In these studies on bischromones we have been able to conclude that the product formation is dependent upon the length of the alkyl chain. This could be due to the intramolecular complex formation between the two-chromone moieties that could be limited by the overlapping of the two nuclei bearing the chromophores. In the case of xyllyl-bischromones the inclusion of a rigid spacer like benzenoid moiety makes the two chromophores to behave independently.

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